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Figure. S1.

Supplementary Figure 1. Effect of AAV9-LAV-BPIFB4 treatment on body weight. Male (A) and female (B) progeria mice exhibited significantly lower body weight at baseline (26-week-old) compared to the Jackson dataset ($n=21$ for both male and female progeria mice). C-D: Line graphs show the body growth in male (C) and female mice (D) assigned to the two treatments. A significant increase in body weight was observed in female mice given AAV9-LAV-BPIFB4 compared with AAV9-GFP controls. However, no group difference was observed in male mice. $N=21$ for each time point. GFP: AAV9-GFP-treated mice; LAV-BPIFB4: AAV9-LAV-BPIFB4-treated mice.

Figure. S2.

Supplementary Figure 2. Progeria mice present preserved cardiac systolic function at an early stage. A-B: systolic indexes of the progeria mice, as indicated by the EF and FS (n=14-15 for progeria mice).

C-E: SV, CO and LV mass in progeria mice. EF: ejection fraction; FS: fractional shortening; SV: stroke volume; CO: cardiac output; and LV: left ventricle.

Echocardiography measurements were analysed using two-way ANOVA to determine both sex and treatment effects. Where sex caused no significant difference, data from male and female mice were pooled for further analysis.

Figure. S3.

Supplementary Figure 3. Measurements of systolic function in progeria mice treated with AAV9-LAV-BPIFB4. A-B: AAV9-LAV-BPIFB4 did not affect EF and FS (n=13-15 for each time point). C-E: Similarly, no effect was noted on SV, CO and LV mass (n=15 for each group). EF: ejection fraction; FS: fractional shortening; SV: stroke volume; CO: cardiac output; LV: left ventricle. GFP: AAV9-GFP-treated mice; LAV-BPIFB4: AAV9-LAV-BPIFB4-treated mice.

Figure. S4.

Supplementary Figure 4. AAV-LAV-BPIFB4 reduced senescence in the liver of HGPS mice.

Liver sections from AAV-GFP- and AAV-LAV-BPIFB4-treated progeria mice were stained. Immunofluorescence staining for the senescence markers p16 and p21 are displayed. The percentage of senescent cells in the liver in AAV9-GFP- and AAV9-LAV-BPIFB4-treated mice were determined, with the data reported as the percentage of p16+ cells (red in ii and pink in iv) or p21+ cells (cyan in both iii and iv) relative to the total cell number (nuclei stained with DAPI, blue in both i and iv). Scale bars are 50 μm.

Figure. S5.

A

B

Supplementary Figure 5. Comparison of human dermal fibroblasts from HGPS patients and unaffected parents. Molecular characterization of HGPS and healthy fibroblasts. Progerin expression in HGPS fibroblasts (n=3) was evaluated by RT-PCR (**A**) and Western blot (**B**). No progerin expression was detected in the healthy controls (n=4). Experiments were performed in two technical replicates for each biological sample. CTR: dermal fibroblasts from unaffected parents. HGPS: dermal fibroblasts from HGPS patients. nt: nucleotide.

Figure. S6.

Supplementary Figure 6. LAV-BPIFB4 expression by lentiviral-mediated infection of HGPS fibroblasts. Expression of LAV-BPIFB4 transgene was analyzed by RT-qPCR and western blot (n=3). E: cells infected with empty vector; L: cells infected with *LAV-BPIFB4*.

Supplementary Table 1. Primary cell lines derived from HGPS patients and healthy controls

Cell Lines	Affected	Age at sampling	Gender
HGADFN167 (HGPS1)	Yes	8 years 5 months	Male
HGADFN169 (HGPS2)	Yes	8 years 6 months	Male
HGADFN367 (HGPS3)	Yes	3 years 6 months	Female
HGMDFN718 (CTR1)	No	42 years 0 months	Female
HGFDFN168 (CTR2)	No	40 years 5 months	Male
HGMDFN368 (CTR3)	No	31 years 7 months	Female
HGFDFN369 (CTR4)	No	33 years 9 months	Male
HGMDFN717 (CTR5)	No	53 years 0 months	Female

Supplementary Table 2. Primer sequences

Genes	Forward	Reverse	Application
<i>BPIFB4</i>	GTGGGTGTCTACCTGAGCT TGT	GCTCAATGACCAGCCGAGG ATA	RT-PCR
<i>ACTA2</i>	ACTGGGACGACATGGAAAAG	CATCTCCAGAGTCCAGCACA	RT-PCR
<i>CNN1</i>	ACTTCATGGACGGCCTCAAA	GTGCCAATTTTGGGTTGACT	RT-PCR
<i>EREG</i>	CTTATCACAGTCGTCGGTTC CAC	GCCATTCAGACTTGCGGCA ACT	RT-PCR
<i>ELN</i>	GGTTGTGTCACCAGAAGCA GCT	CCGTAAGTAGGAATGCCTCC AAC	RT-PCR
<i>COL4A5</i>	CTGCCAGGAATAGGTGTTC AGG	GGAACATCAAGTCCAGGAG GTC	RT-PCR
<i>18S</i>	GTAACCCGTTGAACCCATT	CCATCCAATCGGTAGTAGCG	RT-PCR
<i>LMNA</i> <i>/Progerin</i>	GGTGGTGACGATCTGGGCT	GACGCAGGAAGCCTCCAC	RT-PCR

Supplementary Table 3. Specific antibodies and procedures for Western blotting

Antigen	Company (Catalog Number)	Dilution	Host and Clonality	Incubation Time and Temperature	Secondary Antibody
BPIFB4	Clinsciences	1:1000	Rabbit polyclonal	16 hours, 4°C	ECL Rabbit IgG HPR linked 1:3000
BPIFB4	GeneTex GTX1455	1:1000	Rabbit polyclonal	16 hours, 4°C	ECL Rabbit IgG HPR linked 1:3000
p53	Sial A98895	1:1000	Rabbit polyclonal	16 hours, 4°C	ECL Rabbit IgG HPR linked 1:3000
p21	Abcam ab109199	1:1000	Rabbit polyclonal	16 hours, 4°C	ECL Rabbit IgG HPR linked 1:3000
Lamin A/C	Proteintech 10298-1-AP	1:1000	Rabbit polyclonal	16 hours, 4°C	ECL Rabbit IgG HPR linked 1:3000
Vinculin	Cell Signaling 13901	1:1000	Rabbit polyclonal	16 hours, 4°C	ECL Rabbit IgG HPR linked 1:3000